

Physics Master Poster

Senior 1 to Senior 3 (REB Curriculum)

Senior 1 (S1) Measurement / Gupima	Senior 2 (S2) Light / Umucyo	Senior 3 (S3) Work, Energy & Power / Akazi, Ingufu n'Imbaraga
Forces & Motion / Imbaraga n'Ingendo • Pushing a wheelbarrow / Gusunika igare	Reflection & Refraction / Kugarura no Guhindura umurongo w'Umucyo • Prism experiment / Igerageza rya prisme	Waves & Sound / Imiyanya n'Amajwi • Drums, guitar / Ingoma, gitari
Heat & Temperature / Ubushyuhe n'Ubushyuhe • Boiling water / Kugitsetsa amazi	Electricity & Magnetism / Amashanyarazi n'Imbaraga z'Aimant • Phone charger / Gucomeka telefoni	Pressure in Liquids & Gases / Umuvuduko mu Mazi no mu Gases • Syringe, balloons / Shiringi, umupira

Simple Experiments / Ibigeragezo Byoroshye

- Drop two objects → Gravity / Kurekura ibintu bibiri → Imbaraga z'isi
- Homemade circuit (bulb + battery) / Gucomeka agashanyarazi keza
- Bottle with holes → Pressure in liquids / Icupa rifite imyenge → Umuvuduko w'amazi

“Physics explains the world around you! / Fiziki isobanura isi ikikugose!”